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**A Property For A Counterexample
To Carmichael's Conjecture**

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A PROPERTY FOR A COUNTEREXAMPLE TO CARMICHAËL'S CONJECTURE

Carmichaël has conjectured that:

$(\forall) n \in \mathbb{N}$, $(\exists) m \in \mathbb{N}$, with $m \neq n$, for which $\varphi(n) = \varphi(m)$, where φ is Euler's totient function.

There are many papers on this subject, but the author cites the papers which have influenced him, especially Klee's papers.

Let n be a counterexample to Carmichaël's conjecture.

Grosswald has proved that n is a multiple of 32, Donnelly has pushed the result to a multiple of 2^{14} , and Klee to a multiple of $2^{42} \cdot 3^{47}$, Smarandache has shown that n is a multiple of $2^2 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 7^2 \cdot 43^2$. Masai & Valette have bounded $n > 10^{10000}$.

In this note we will extend these results to: n is a multiple of a product of a very large number of primes.

We construct a recurrent set M such that:

a) the elements $2, 3 \in M$;

b) if the distinct elements $2, 3, q_1, \dots, q_r \in M$ and $p = 1 + 2^a \cdot 3^b \cdot q_1 \cdots q_r$ is a prime, where $a \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 41\}$ and $b \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 46\}$, then $p \in M$; $r \geq 0$;

c) any element belonging to M is obtained only by the utilization (a finite number of times) of the rules a) or b).

Of course, all elements from M are primes.

Let n be a multiple of $2^{42} \cdot 3^{47}$;

if $5 \nmid n$ then there exists $m = 5n/4 \neq n$ such that $\varphi(n) = \varphi(m)$; hence

$5 \mid n$; whence $5 \in M$;

if $5^2 \nmid n$ then there exists $m = 4n/5 \neq n$ with our property; hence $5^2 \mid n$;

analogously, if $7 \nmid n$ we can take $m = 7n/6 \neq n$, hence $7 \mid n$; if $7^2 \nmid n$ we can take $m = 6n/7 \neq n$; whence $7 \in M$ and $7^2 \mid n$; etc.

The method continues until it isn't possible to add any other prime to M , by its construction.

For example, from the 168 primes smaller than 1000, only 17 of them do not belong to M (namely: 101, 151, 197, 251, 401, 491, 503, 601, 607, 677, 701, 727, 751, 809, 883, 907, 983); all other 151 primes belong to M .

Note $M = \{2, 3, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s, \dots\}$, then n is a multiple of $2^{42} \cdot 3^{47} \cdot p_1^2 \cdot p_2^2 \cdots p_s^2 \cdots$

From our example, it results that M contains at least 151 elements, hence $s \geq 149$.

If M is infinite then there is no counterexample n , whence Carmichaël's conjecture is solved.

(The author conjectures M is infinite.)

Using a computer it is possible to find a very large number of primes, which divide n , using the construction method of M , and trying to find a new prime p if $p - 1$ is a product of primes only from M .

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